

Design and Test of a Circularly Polarized Microstrip Antenna Array for a Sentinel-1 SAR Active Reflector with co- and cross- Polarization Capability

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Abstract—This paper reports the design and implementation of a circularly polarized microstrip array antenna operating in C-band. The antenna was designed to upgrade a C-band active reflector to be used with the ESA Sentinel-1 satellite SAR. The use of circular polarization improves the exploitation of the single polarization active reflectors allowing their use for the complete set of linearly polarized radar images available from the SAR acquisitions. This improvement can be done simply by replacing one of its two antennas. High gain, low cost, and a fine axial ratio are the main requirements of this prototype. Results show a good agreement between simulations and measurements, moreover, the close-range operational test done with the active reflector using the proposed antenna demonstrates the feasibility of the idea described in this work.

Index Terms — Microstrip Antenna, Antenna Array, Sentinel-1, circular polarization, Active Reflectors.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the EuCAP 2019 symposium the authors presented the design and implementation of an active reflector [1] whose main characteristics are reported in [2]. In this implement the receiving and transmitting antenna consist of two Linear Polarization (LP) array antennas. Considering the present Sentinel-1 imaging configuration, this choice limits the use of the active reflector only to a single acquisition configuration to be selected between co-pol (VV) or cross-pol (VH) mode. The antenna here reported was designed to upgrade this active reflector, allowing the capability to give both a co- and cross- polarization response simultaneously with a single retransmitting antenna. In fact, considering that the circular polarization is a combination of the two linear polarizations, the re-transmitting antenna of the active reflector can provide, although with a lower signal strength, a high Radar Cross Section both in the VV and VH images sequentially acquired by the Satellite. This improves the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images interpretation and calibration with a full exploitation of the whole satellite data. This paper resumes the main characteristics of a novel CP microstrip Antenna Array antenna including a preliminary test of the new active reflector at short range.

II. DESIGN CHOICE AND EXPECTED PERFORMANCE

The goal of the design is a 4x4 array with circular polarized (CP) patches. The design of a CP antenna array can be made using different approaches as recalled in [1]: composed of individual CP elements [3] or using linearly polarized (LP) elements conveniently phased and fed [4-6]. In the case here described the array is composed of individual CP elements. The single patch is different from those used in [1], in the design here presented the element is square, and the CP is obtained using a dual-feed configuration and 90° of phase shift between ports, which generates CP radiation with low cross polarization and higher axial ratio bandwidth. This better axial ratio bandwidth is obtained at the cost of increased size of ground plane to accommodate the feed network. One requirement in our prototype is to provide a high gain to compensate the reduction of the active reflector's RCS, caused by the 3 dB lower linear radiation present at the antenna's terminal. Due to the increased size of the re-transmitting antenna and the required compactness of the device, the coupling between the two has been checked to avoid the occurrence of signal loop [2] which compromise the correct working of the device. The array, shown in Fig.1, has a feeding network which uses Wilkinson power dividers, in order to reach a good bandwidth for the axial ratio [7-9], and two 90° phase difference lines feed each patch to obtain circular polarization.

The feeding network has been designed and fabricated using the dielectric substrate Arlon 25N with a thickness of 0.5 mm, dielectric constant 3.38 and loss tangent of 0.0025, that give us a width of 1.15 mm for the 50 ohms lines. For the patches the substrate is Taconic RF35 with thickness 1.52 mm, dielectric constant 3.5 and loss tangent 0.0018. This combination of dielectric constant and thickness is suitable for the required bandwidth, and the low losses of this material help to improve the performance. The patches are placed over the ground plane of the feeding network. Then, the connection between the feeding network and the

patches has been implemented through small pins of diameter 0.6 mm and small holes have been introduced in the ground plane to allow the connection. These pins are soldered to the patches and feeding network.

Instead of a full piece for all the patches, we have cut each patch separately, in this way we reduce the cost of material, and we also reduce the tolerances in the central frequency produced when copper in the dielectric is removed with a milling machine due to the groove produced in the substrate. In addition, the obtained bandwidth is slightly higher because of the reduced effective dielectric constant of the patch. Fig. 1 shows the array design where the up and down faces of the board are identified by different colors, with a size of 165 x 165 mm and thickness 2 mm. Two circular polarized antennas were implemented, left-hand (LHCP) and right-hand (RHCP). Here we show the results for the RHCP version.

Figure 1. Transparent view of the two layers of the designed array: the darker color indicates the feeding network face.

III. SIMULATION AND MEASUREMENT OF THE ANTENNA

As a preliminary step, the array performance has been simulated using ANSYS software [10]. Fig. 2 shows the axial ratio (AR) of the array, of main concern for the use of this antenna, as a function of the frequency, simulated for different directions close to the perpendicular. We recall that the operating band used by European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1 SAR span 100 MHz centered at 5.405 GHz. The AR is traced in Fig. 2 for different directions centered in the end-fire (theta angles) both for phi=90° and phi=0°. The simulation shows that we can expect an AR lower than 1dB for directions with theta < 15°.

Figure 2 . AR of the array as a function of the frequency simulated for different elevation directions (0° and ±15°) and for phi=0 and Phi=90°.

The array has been tested in an anechoic chamber where AR, S₁₁, radiation pattern and the gain were measured. In Fig. 3 the simulated and measured S₁₁ vs the frequency is shown. There is a significant shift between the measured data with respect to the simulated ones probably due to the manufacturing, in any case the value in the requested bandwidth is compliant with the requirement < -20 dB.

Figure 3. Simulated (dashed line) and measured (solid line) insertion losses.

Fig. 4 shows the measured AR vs frequency compared to the corresponding simulated trend. It is worth noting that the AR, although not coincident with the expected simulated curve as the same trend and it maintains below 1 dB over the entire required bandwidth.

Figure 4 . Axial ratio as a function of the frequency simulated and measured for the perpendicular direction.

Finally, Fig. 5 shows the simulated and measured gain. The value is lower than the expected one but also in this case the trend of the simulated and experimental data is the same. Some elements such as the connector and soldered pins, the higher losses of the material than the theoretical values and the sensitivity of the measurement process could explain this difference. As far as the antenna pattern is concerned, Fig. 6a and 6b show the simulated and measured radiation pattern for $\phi=0^\circ$ and $\phi=90^\circ$ respectively at the central frequency of 5.405 GHz.

The radiation patterns of the antenna confirm a satisfactory implementation of the prototype.

Figure 5. Realized gain simulated and measured for the perpendicular direction.

a)

b)

Figure 6 . Antenna radiation pattern of the array, simulated (dashed line) and measured (solid line). a) $\phi=0^\circ$, b) $\phi=90^\circ$

IV. PRELIMINARY TEST OF THE ACTIVE REFLECTOR AT SHORT RANGE

A first test of the active reflector with the new antenna has been carried out using a Vectorial Network Analyzer (VNA) based transceiver to simulate the Sentinel-1 signal. Details on this procedure are available in [2]. The test consists of transmitting a continuous wave step frequency signal widely covering the required bandwidth, from 5 GHz to 6 GHz, and measuring the backscattering from the active reflector located at a far field range, 6.2 m far from the transceiver antennas. Fig. 7 shows a picture of the active reflector with the new antenna used as the retransmitting antenna of the active reflector. The response obtained transmitting two different linear polarization configurations, co- and cross- pol, VV and VH respectively, is compared to

verify the radar cross section in the two cases. Fig. 8 shows the range profile, amplitude of the received signal obtained after transforming frequency data to time domain as a function of the distance from the transceiver. The range resolution, i.e the distance corresponding to one radar bin unit is 0.15 m. Observing Fig. 8, it could be noted that the first peak is due to the antennas coupling and it represents the actual location of the range first bin. The difference of amplitude obtained in the two configuration is lower than 0.5 dB a value which confirm the satisfactory implementation of the antenna and its integration with the device.

Figure 7. Picture of the active reflector where the RHCP antenna (transmitting) has been mounted.

Figure 8. Amplitude range profile of the acquisitions carried out using the VNA based transceiver. The red and green lines indicate the active reflector response with a cross pol and co-pol transceiver configuration respectively. Bin 66 corresponds to a distance to the radar of 6.4 ± 0.15 m.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A 4x4 patch array aimed at providing a circular polarized antenna for Active Corner Reflector to be used with Sentinel-1 satellite data has been designed. The simulation results show a good agreement with the required operating bandwidth and axial ratio. The first operational test at close-range of the active reflector using this novel antenna also confirm a satisfactory behavior of the entire system. This idea paves the road for future implementations of low-cost circularly polarized active reflector for satellite imaging applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G Luzi, E Fernandez, FM Perez, M Crosetto, "[A Low Cost Active Corner Reflector to assist Snow Monitoring through Sentinel/1 images.](#)" 2020 14th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), 1-4.
- [2] G Luzi, PF Espín-López, F Mira Pérez, O Monserrat, M Crosetto, "[A Low-Cost Active Reflector for Interferometric Monitoring Based on Sentinel-1 SAR Images.](#)" Sensors 21 (6), 2008.
- [3] K. S. Kwok and C. H. Chan, "Circularly polarized patch antenna array for satellite communication in Ku band," 2016 10th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), 2016, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/EuCAP.2016.7481863.
- [4] R. Caso, A. Buffi, M. Rodriguez Pino, P. Nepa and G. Manara, "A Novel Dual-Feed Slot-Coupling Feeding Technique for Circularly Polarized Patch Arrays," in IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, vol. 9, pp. 183-186, 2010, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2010.2044864.
- [5] J. Xu, W. Hong, Z. H. Jiang, H. Zhang and K. Wu, "Low-Profile Wideband Vertically Folded Slotted Circular Patch Array for Ka-Band Applications," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 68, no. 9, pp. 6844-6849, Sept. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2020.3005028.
- [6] R. F. Ma et al., "Theory, Design, and Verification of Dual-Circularly Polarized Dual-Beam Arrays With Independent Control of Polarization: A Generalization of Sequential Rotation Arrays," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 1369-1382, March 2021, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2020.3016500.
- [7] Bai, B.; Zhang, Z.; Li, X.; Sun, C.; Liu, Y., "Integration of Microstrip Slot Array Antenna with Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells." Sensors 2020, 20, 6257. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20216257>
- [8] Wu, T, Li, J-L, Zhang, S, Chen, J., "Design of broadband circularly polarized metasurface antenna array with gain enhancement." Int J RF Microw Comput Aided Eng. 2020; 30:e22446. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mmce.22446>.
- [9] Y. Shen, S. Zhou, G. Huang and T. Chio, "A Compact Dual Circularly Polarized Microstrip Patch Array With Interlaced Sequentially Rotated Feed," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 4933-4936, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2016.2600747.
- [10] [Ansys HFSS | 3D High Frequency Simulation Software](#)